

GATEWAYS TO ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: DEVELOPING A TAXONOMY FOR AI SERVICE PLATFORMS

Categorization of platforms

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific (12)		industry-unspecific (19)		
	Activity focus	activity-specific (4)		activity-unspecific (27)		
	Platform use	continuous (9)	continuous and on-demand (11)	on-demand (9)	none (2)	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service (3)	application development and deployment service (13)	hybrid service (3)	ready-to-use service (9)	
		none (3)				
	Complementary services	yes (24)			no (7)	
	Complementary resources	yes (10)			no (21)	
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes (18)			no (13)	
	Graphical interface	click through (20)	click through and drag and drop (4)	drag and drop (5)	none (2)	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors (7)	selected complementors and crowd (2)	crowd (5)	none (17)	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource (4)	resource and service (3)	service (7)	none (17)	

Figure 1. A taxonomy of AI service platforms.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 2. Afresh.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 3. Algorithmia AI Layer.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 4. Amazon Sage Maker.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 5. Artivatic.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 6. AWS Marketplace.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 7. Ayasdi.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 8. BigML.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 9. Civis Analytics.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 10. CreateML.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 11. Data Robot.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 12. Dataiku.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 13. Deep Cognition.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 14. Domino Datalab.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 15. Figure Eight.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 16. Fritz.ai.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 17. Google Cloud AI Platform.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 18. IBM Watson.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 19. *Inbenta.*

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 20. InfoSys Nia.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 21. KAI.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 22. Meya.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 23. MLJAR.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 24. MS Azure AI.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 25. Nuance Marketplace.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 26. Peltarion.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 27. Payment.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 28. Rainbird.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 29. Receptiviti.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 30. Salesforce Einstein.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 31. Uptake.

	Dimension	Characteristics				
Customer context	Industry focus	industry-specific		industry-unspecific		
	Activity focus	activity-specific		activity-unspecific		
	Platform use	continuous	continuous and on-demand	on-demand	none	
AI service platform's offering	AI service model	application deployment service	application development and deployment service	hybrid service	ready-to-use service	
		none				
	Complementary services	yes		no		
	Complementary resources	yes		no		
	Pricing model	one-off payment	regularly based on variable rates	regularly based on fixed rates	freemium	free of charge
	Code-based interaction	yes		no		
	Graphical interface	click through	click through and drag and drop	drag and drop	none	
Third-party integration	Integrated complementor	selected complementors	selected complementors and crowd	crowd	none	
	Integrated complementor offering	resource	resource and service	service	none	

Figure 32. WorkFusion.